

APPENDIX 3 - USEFULNESS AND EASE OF USE ASSESSMENT QUESTIONNAIRE – TAM

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Part 1 - Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) of the CPRP

1) Was it easy to LEARN how to use the catalog?

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Agree somewhat
- Strongly Agree

2) Was it easy to GAIN skill in using the catalog?

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Agree somewhat
- Strongly Agree

3) Is it easy to REMEMBER how to use the catalog?

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Agree somewhat
- Strongly Agree

4) Do I find the catalog easy to USE?

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Agree somewhat
- Strongly Agree

Part 2 - Perceived Usefulness (PU) of CPRP

5) Did using the catalog make it easier to ELICIT requirements?

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Agree somewhat

Strongly Agree

6) Was using the catalog helpful in eliciting requirements?

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Agree somewhat
- Strongly Agree

7) Did using the catalog make it easier to specify requirements?

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Agree somewhat
- Strongly Agree

8) Was using the catalog helpful for specifying requirements?

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Agree somewhat
- Strongly Agree

9) Did the catalog help in understanding the LGPD (Brazilian General Data Protection Law) for eliciting and specifying requirements?

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Agree somewhat
- Strongly Agree

10) Can the catalog be useful in professional practice?

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Agree somewhat
- Strongly Agree

Part 3 – Essay Questions

5) What are the main challenges perceived when using the Catalog?

6) What are the main perceived benefits of using the Catalog?
